

Data Management Plan Information

Investigating Missing Citations in COCI

The purpose of this research is to find the publishers responsible for the missing citations in COCI (the OpenCitations Index of Crossref open DOI-to-DOI citations) by sending incorrect metadata to Crossref, the publishers to whom such invalid citations point to, and the number of previously invalid citations which are currently valid.

Funder

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Open Science Project 2020/2021

Organisations

University of Bologna

Researchers

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Datasets

Title: Missing Citations in COCI: Publishers Analytics Result

Template: Horizon 2020

This dataset contains the results of our investigation on the missing citation data in COCI. Specifically, it includes, in JSON format: the names and identifiers of the publishers involved in the citations (either as the publishers of the citing DOI or the publisher of the cited DOIs); the numbers of the valid and invalid citations they are responsible for as the publishers of the valid citing DOI; the number of the valid and invalid citations they are involved in as publishers of the cited DOI; the total number of DOIs now valid; the list of still invalid citations and the list of now valid citations.

Dataset Description

1.2 Data Summary

1.2.2 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

["To obtain information", "To improve a product", "To combine with other data"]

Comment: Our aim is to investigate missing citations in COCI, so our purpose is to generate and share information related to this issue by retrieving publishers involved in the citations. Furthermore, we are combining input data with other data obtained through the DOI and Crossref APIs, such as the name of the publishers.

1.2.3 What types of data will the project generate/collect?

["sample or specimen data", "derived or compiled (e.g.", "text mining", "3D models)"]

We extract and analyse data from an already existing source, which is a sample of all invalid DOIs which constitute missing citations for COCI.

1.2.4 What formats of data will the project generate/collect?

["Text files - MS Word docs", ".txt files", "PDF", "RTF", "XML (Extensible Markup Language)", "Other"]

The input and processed data is stored in a CSV file. This dataset as output data of the project is in JSON format.

1.2.6 What is the origin of the data?

["Secondary data"]

1.2.7 What is the expected size of the data?

MB (megabyte)

Comment: Since the input file weighs 60 MB, then a greater file size is expected for the output - because we are also collecting additional data from other sources - but not greater than MB.

1.2.8 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

["Researchers", "Research communities", "Decision makers"]

The data can be used by the decision makers and the researchers at COCI for future policy making. Also, this data could be useful for other researchers from the scientific community within the field of Scientometrics.

2.3 Reusable Data

2.3.1 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Yes

Peroni, S. (2021). Citations to invalid DOI-identified entities obtained from processing DOI-to-DOI citations to add in COCI (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.4625300>

["To compare and combine with other data", "To follow-up research on a specific area"]

3.4.2 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.4.2.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

We use metadata through Zenodo, which uses DataCite as standard vocabulary. Further, we'll evaluate in a second moment whether or not adding further files specifying more detailed metadata provided by us.

3.4.2.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

In case we decide to provide further metadata in separate additional files, we will select an appropriate metadata schema to follow.

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.4.2.4 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://schema.datacite.org/>

Through Zenodo, we implicitly use DataCite Metadata Schema.

3.4.2.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Comment: Zenodo metadata are free of charge. In case we'll add further metadata, also these latter will be free-of-charge, since we work in an open science environment that was developed under FAIR principles.

3.4.2.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Comment: All data and metadata provided in our project are harvestable and stored in Zenodo and Github, whose metadata are indeed harvestable. In case we'll add further metadata, also these latter will be harvestable.

3.4.2.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

3.4.2.8 Please provide more details and examples on used naming conversions

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Snake_case

Delimiter-separated words for property names (snake case)

3.4.2.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

3.4.2.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

Yes

Comment: As soon as the dataset will be finalised, we will publish it on Zenodo platform. Therefore, a DOI (digital object identifier) will be assigned to the dataset.

3.4.2.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.4.2.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

Yes

Comment: The metadata we provide through Zenodo are indexed and made searchable by the platform itself.

3.4.2.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

OpenAIRE

3.4.2.15 Will you use standardised formats for your data?

Yes

```
[{"id":"fileformat:pronom-generic/231e9c33-6940-479a-a125-4ea972254c3d","label":"JSON Data Interchange Format","source":"","uri":""}]
```

3.4.2.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Comment: We create a dataset which is reusable for everyone for free. Further, all file formats involved in the creation of this dataset are non-proprietary formats that could be opened and used through any editor.

3.4.2.21 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

Comment: Any open-source text editor can be used to access the JSON dataset we generate.

3.4.2.22 Please describe if data require proprietary tools to access the data?

Not at all. All file formats used are non-proprietary and thus accessible without the necessity to use any specific tool in particular.

3.4.2.23 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

Yes

Comment: The metadata used to describe this dataset provide information also about qualitative attributes of the resource we make available. For example: file size, upload date and version.

3.4.3 Making data openly accessible

3.4.3.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No

Comment: Data are neither personal nor confidential, so we do not think that there could be issues in sharing them directly to others.

3.4.3.3 Will your data be openly accessible?

all

3.4.3.5 How will the data be made available?

["Project website", "University repository", "Repository of Archive"]

[{"id":"datarepo:re3data/r3d100010375","label":"GitHub","source":"","uri":"https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100010375"}]

Zenodo

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3.4.3.6 Please provide URL/Name of used data repositories

<https://github.com/open-sci/2020-2021-the-leftovers-20-code>

The data we produced as output stored in this dataset are available in the project website (<https://open-sci.github.io/2020-2021-the-leftovers-20-code/index.html>), on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4735638>) and also in the GitHub repository of our software, which title is: 2020-2021-the-leftovers-20-code

3.4.3.7 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

secure with backup and recovery

Comment: Both Zenodo and Github provide different ways and processes to backup data, and this is one of the reasons why we selected these two platforms to store our datasets.

3.4.3.10 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

No

As stated in "www.openaire.eu" website, Zenodo allows researchers to deposit research artifacts and doesn't impose any requirements on format, size, access restrictions or licence and it neither has restrictions on funders or nations. Further, it is free to use for all research outputs.

3.4.3.13 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?
at end of project

Comment: In the case we will find relevant auxiliary data, we will make it available in the same GitHub repository of the code.

3.4.4 Making data interoperable

3.4.4.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for your data?

No

3.4.4.2 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.4.5 Increase data reuse

3.4.5.2 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?
immediately

3.4.5.5 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your data?

[{"id":"CC-BY-4.0","label":"Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International","source":"","uri":null}]

3.4.5.6 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of your data?

Yes

Comment: All the data we use and elaborate in our workflow are provided by referenced and trustable resources: OpenCitations' COCI for the input dataset (i.e.: invalid_dois.csv); Crossref API services for doi prefixes for publishers' identification; doi.org API service to check DOIs validity.

3.4.5.7 Describe the data quality assurance processes

["Use of tools for automatic checks"]

Comment: Since quality assurance checks can be facilitated by the use of tools, we have to specify that we are using API services to generate this dataset.

3.4.5.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

Yes

Comment: This dataset will be kept accessible (as it already is) from the original repositories in which it has been stored since the beginning of the project. We are open for issues opened by users on the GitHub platform and support data reuse by exploiting a well-established platform as Zenodo. This dataset will be also reachable through a project website.

3.4.5.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

Up to 5 years

4.5 Allocation of resources

4.5.2 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

["Use of institution infrastructure", "Collaboration with other Projects"]

4.5.3 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?

No

Comment: All the members of the team will be responsible for the management of the data.

4.5.4 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the project data

```
[{"reference":"0000-0001-5486-7070","hint":null,"name":"Arianna Moretti (orcid:0000-0001-5486-7070)","label":null,"id":null,"tag":"ORCID","key":"orcid","status":0}, {"reference":"0000-0003-4114-074X","hint":null,"name":"Nooshin Shahidzadeh Asadi (orcid:0000-0003-4114-074X)","label":null,"id":null,"tag":"ORCID","key":"orcid","status":0}, {"reference":"0000-0002-6279-3830","hint":null,"name":"Sara Coppini (orcid:0000-0002-6279-3830)","label":null,"id":null,"tag":"ORCID","key":"orcid","status":0}, {"reference":"0000-0002-9812-4065","hint":null,"name":"Alessia null (orcid:0000-0002-9812-4065)","label":null,"id":null,"tag":"ORCID","key":"orcid","status":0}]
```

Arianna Moretti (orcid:0000-0001-5486-7070), Nooshin Shahidzadeh Asadi (orcid:0000-0003-4114-074X), Sara Coppini (orcid:0000-0002-6279-3830), Alessia null (orcid:0000-0002-9812-4065)

Comment: All group members are equally reasonably responsible for the management of the data in every step of the process.

4.5.5 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

["Other"]

5.6 Data Security

5.6.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.7.2 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

7.8 Other

7.8.2 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: Code for Missing Citations Analysis in COCI

Template: Horizon 2020

This dataset contains the complete source code for the investigative research applied to the COCI missing citation data. The source code includes the processes to study citations sent and received by each publisher.

Dataset Description

1.2 Data Summary

1.2.2 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

["To obtain information", "To combine with other data"]

Comment: The software gathers, combines and analyses data.

1.2.3 What types of data will the project generate/collect?

["text mining", "derived or compiled (e.g., text mining, 3D models)"]

We collect data from an already existing dataset of the invalid citation data.

1.2.4 What formats of data will the project generate/collect?

["C", "Software - Java, C, Python"]

There is an original CSV file as source for data collection and we generate python code.

1.2.6 What is the origin of the data?

["Primary data"]

1.2.7 What is the expected size of the data?

KB (kilobyte)

Comment: The python code is expected to be quite small.

1.2.8 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

["Researchers", "Research communities", "Decision makers"]

The software can be reused by the decision makers at COCI and for research purposes.

2.3 Reusable Data

2.3.1 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Yes

We re-used python libraries and already available materials in the main software: json library (https://github.com/python/cpython/blob/3.9/Lib/json/__init__.py), csv library (<https://github.com/python/cpython/blob/3.9/Lib/csv.py>), re library (<https://github.com/python/cpython/blob/3.9/Lib/re.py>), os library (<https://github.com/python/cpython/blob/3.9/Lib/os.py>), datetime (<https://github.com/python/cpython/blob/3.9/Lib/datetime.py>), unit tests (https://github.com/python/cpython/blob/3.9/Lib/unittest/__init__.py) and finally “requests” to deal with APIs requests. We re-used some javascript libraries in order to realise the graphics with the final data: D3.js (<https://d3js.org/>)

d3.v7.min.js), Chart.js (<https://cdn.jsdelivr.net/npm/chart.js>), HighCharts (<https://code.highcharts.com/highcharts.js>).

["To follow-up research on a specific area", "To develop new products/ services"]

3.4.2 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.4.2.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

We use metadata through Zenodo, which uses DataCite as standard vocabulary. Further, we'll evaluate in a second moment whether or not adding further files specifying more detailed metadata provided by us.

3.4.2.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

In case we decide to provide further metadata in separate additional files, we will select an appropriate metadata schema to follow.

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.4.2.4 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://schema.datacite.org/>

Through Zenodo, we implicitly use DataCite Metadata Schema.

3.4.2.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Comment: Zenodo metadata are free of charge. In case we'll add further metadata, also these latter will be available online and free-of-charge.

3.4.2.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Comment: All data and metadata provided in our project are harvestable and stored in Zenodo and Github, whose metadata are indeed harvestable. In case we'll add further metadata, also these latter will be harvestable.

3.4.2.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

3.4.2.8 Please provide more details and examples on used naming conversions

<https://www.python.org/dev/peps/pep-0008/>

PEP 8

3.4.2.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Comment: We use version numbers for the dataset, which is a software, since we publish it on Zenodo on each update.

3.4.2.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

Yes

Comment: As soon as the code will be finalised, we will publish it on Zenodo platform. Therefore, a DOI (digital object identifier) will be assigned to the source.

3.4.2.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.4.2.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

Yes

Comment: The metadata we provide through Zenodo are indexed and made searchable by the platform itself.

3.4.2.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

OpenAIRE

3.4.2.15 Will you use standardised formats for your data?

Yes

Python Script File

3.4.2.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Comment: We create python code which is reusable for everyone for free. Further, all our file formats are non-proprietary formats that could be opened and used through any editor.

3.4.2.21 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

Comment: As an example open-source text editor, Atom, among many, can be used to access the python code we generate.

3.4.2.22 Please describe if data require proprietary tools to access the data?

Not at all. All file formats used are non-proprietary and thus accessible without the necessity to use any specific tool in particular.

3.4.2.23 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

Yes

Comment: The metadata used to describe this dataset provide information also about qualitative attributes of the resource we make available. For example: file size, upload date and version.

3.4.3 Making data openly accessible

3.4.3.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No

3.4.3.3 Will your data be openly accessible?

all

3.4.3.5 How will the data be made available?

["Project website", "University repository", "Repository of Archive"]

GitHub

Zenodo, Github

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.4.3.6 Please provide URL/Name of used data repositories

<https://github.com/open-sci/2020-2021-the-leftovers-20-code>

2020-2021-the-leftovers-20-code

3.4.3.7 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

secure with backup and recovery

Comment: Both Zenodo and Github provide different ways and processes to backup data, and this is the reason why we selected these two platforms to store our datasets.

3.4.3.10 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

No

As stated in "www.openaire.eu" website, Zenodo allows researchers to deposit research artifacts and doesn't impose any requirements on format, size, access restrictions or licence and it neither has restrictions on funders or nations. Further, it is free to use for all research outputs.

3.4.3.13 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

at end of project

Comment: In the case we will find relevant auxiliary data, we will make it available in the same GitHub repository of the code.

3.4.4 Making data interoperable

3.4.4.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for your data?

No

3.4.4.2 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.4.5 Increase data reuse

3.4.5.2 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?
immediately

3.4.5.5 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your data?

ISC License

3.4.5.6 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of your data?

Yes

Comment: We have developed unit tests, which can be considered as documented procedures for quality assurance of the data for this kind of dataset (python file).

3.4.5.6 Please provide URL with the documented procedures
<https://docs.python.org/3/library/unittest.html>

3.4.5.7 Describe the data quality assurance processes
["Consistency verified with data models and standards"]

Comment: Unit tests

3.4.5.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?
Yes

Comment: This dataset will be kept accessible (as it already is) from the original repositories in which it has been stored since the beginning of the project. we are open for issues opened by users on the GitHub platform and support data reuse by exploiting a well-established platform as Zenodo. This dataset will be also reachable through a project website.

3.4.5.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?
Up to 5 years

4.5 Allocation of resources

4.5.2 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?
["Use of institution infrastructure", "Collaboration with other Projects"]

4.5.3 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?
No

Comment: All the members of the team will be responsible for the management of the data.

4.5.4 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the project data
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Comment: All group members are equally reasonably responsible for the management of the data in every step of the process.

4.5.5 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

["Other"]

Comment: GitHub is a provider of Internet hosting for software development, and since it is the largest host of source code in the world we are confident that by using this tool we will ensure data reuse.

5.6 Data Security

5.6.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.7 Ethical aspects

6.7.2 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.7.3 What are the methods used for processing sensitive/personal data?

["Not available"]

Comment: Since we don't handle sensitive/personal data we don't use specific methods to process them.

7.8 Other

7.8.2 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No